

Relation Between a Microcanonical Derivation of the MB Distribution and a Kind of Reaction Balance

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In (1), a microcanonical derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution is provided using a factorial expression, Stirling approximation and the notion of n atoms, each of which can hold an integer number of e units of energy. The total number of energy units is u , so $E=e*u$. Given that a microcanonical distribution is used, there is no need for any maximization of entropy subject to constraints. (1) counts the number of scenarios using $n-1$ partitions of u units, i.e. $(n-1+u)! / \{ (n-1)! u! \}$. The objective of (1) is to show that $\ln(p_j)$ is proportional to $j*e$, i.e. e_j which leads to the MB distribution.

Here we argue that $\ln(p_j)$ must be proportional to e_j by using a kind of reaction balance argument as well as a lack of information notion. In other words, two distinct notions are required.. If j energy atoms are numbered and k energy atoms are also numbered separately, then one may consider for each ensemble copy, a single atom with j combining with an atom of k to create an energy $(j+k)*e$. Two principles are required. If all energy distributions carry the same weight, as in a microcanonical distribution, then the number of j atoms * the number of k atoms should equal the number of l atoms * the number of m atoms if: $j+k = l+m$. Otherwise, there is special information linked to j,k producing the same energy as l,m . The “kind” of reaction balance, however, is a separate notion. We consider all atoms with $(j+k)e$ energy as being numbered as well as each j atom and each k atom. We consider an ensemble copy for each reaction with a k (using the numbered atoms) and argue that each unique pairing must match a unique member of the numbered set of $(j+k)$ atoms. Thus, unique pair of j,k atoms combine and the unique mapped $j+k$ atom decays to yield a j atom and k atom with the same numbering as the originals which combined.

In such a case, one uses unnormalized probability, i.e. the number of j atoms, the number of k atoms and the number of $j+k$ atoms. We argue that reaction balance implies that: (number of j) * (number of k) = (number of $j+k$ atoms). Using the lack of information notion, however, implies that the number of j and number of k atoms may be replaced by the number of l and number of m atoms if $l+m = j+k$.

Thus, taking \ln of this equation yields a sum which should match $e_j + e_k = e_{(j+k)}$. We argue that $\ln\{ p_j \text{ unnormalized} \} = \text{constant} * e_j$, from which the MB distribution arises. As a result, one does not need to explicitly create a factorial expression or use Stirling’s approximation, we argue.

Microcanonical Factorial Approach of (1)

The basic approach of (1) is to argue that if one has n atoms with u units of energy e , then the number of ways to assign different sets of e 's to each atom (such that the total is u) is:

$$(n-1+u)! / \{ (n-1)! u! \} \quad ((1))$$

One has $n-1$ partitions breaking the u units of e into different groupings. Each grouping has the same weight in the microcanonical approach, hence ((1)) has meaning.

The next step is to find p_j , which is proportional to the number of atoms with j units. This is said to be proportional to the first atom having j units. Then, one has $u-j$ units of energy left and so:

P_j is proportional to ((1)) with $u \rightarrow u - j$ ((2))

The goal is to show that $\ln(p_j)$ is proportional to j . ((1)) does a full calculation, but this is the main goal and so we only focus on it.)

Using Stirling's approximation, one has:

$\ln(p_j)$ proportional to: $(n-1 + u - j) \ln\{(n-1 + u - j)\} - (n-1) \ln(n-1) - (u-j) \ln(u-j)$ ((3))

One is concerned with terms containing j , but j is tiny compared to u in most cases and so the leading j dependent terms of ((3)) are (for $j \ll u$) (Also $n-1$ is approx= n)

$\ln(p_j)$ proportional to $(n+u-j) \ln(n+u) - (u-j) \ln(u)$ ((4))

One may see that: $\ln(p_j)$ is linked with $F(n,u) + j F_1(n,u)$ where F and F_1 are functions ((5))

Thus, $\ln(p_j)$ is essentially proportional to j leading to the MB distribution.

One may see full calculations in (1), but we argue that this is the key of the argument.

Use of a Kind of Reaction Balance

We ask if the notion of a microcanonical distribution allows one to obtain: $\ln(p_j)$ proportional to j without writing any factorial expression or using Stirling's approximation. In order to consider this kind of approach, two main notions are required.

We first consider n atoms. Some have energy j , some energy k and some energy, $j+k$. There are other energies, l and m , however, that also add to $j+k$. The question then becomes:

Is: $\text{number}(j) * \text{number}(k) = \text{number}(l) * \text{number}(m)$? ((6))

If ((6)) holds, then an energy $j+k$ can decay with equal probability into any $x+y$ such that:

$J+k = x+y$ ((7))

We argue that ((7)) is equivalent to the notion of a microcanonical distribution (minimal information), but the idea of a kind of reaction balance is a second notion.

Given ((6)), we only focus on a set (j,k) and atoms with energy j+k. We number each of the atoms with j energy and those with k energy separately, as well as those with j+k. We consider a single combination of a j with k in one ensemble copy and argue that for reaction balance, this unique combination must map to a unique numbered atom of the j+k set. In other words, a unique pair of j,k may combine to create an e(j+k) at the same time as the uniquely mapped e decays to j,k with the unique number of the atoms linked with j and k energies. This, we argue is reaction balance, i.e. equilibrium.

Thus:

$$\text{Number of (j+k) atoms} = \text{number(j)} * \text{number(k)} \quad ((8))$$

If one combines this with ((6)), then:

$$\text{Number of (j+k) atoms} = \text{number(i)} * \text{number(m)} \text{ as long as } j+k=i + m \quad ((8))$$

Now the number of x atoms is the unnormalized p_x , where x is the energy of the atom. ((8)) implies that by taking ln:

$$\ln(p_{j+k}) = \ln(p_i) + \ln(p_m) \text{ for any } i+m = j+k \quad ((9))$$

We argue then that given that $e_{j+k} = e_i + e_m$:

$\ln(p_i)$ is proportional to i, from which follows the MB distribution.

In such a scenario, there is no need for a factorial statement or Stirling's approximation.

Conclusion

The author of (1) provides an interesting derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution using the microcanonical distribution. This requires the use of a factorial expression and Stirling's approximation. We try to argue that the equal weight assigned to any energy distribution in the microcanonical case is equivalent to two statements. The first is that given $\text{number(j)} * \text{number(k)}$, this is equal to $\text{number(l)} * \text{number(m)}$ if $j+k = l+m$, otherwise there would be special information linked with the constituents of e_{j+k} and this would contradict the microcanonical view. Here number(j) is the number of atoms with j units of energy, etc.

The second notion is linked with comparing j,k atoms with j+k atoms. We label each j atom and each k atom separately and consider a separate ensemble copy for each possible unique pairing. We argue that each unique pairing must map to uniquely numbered j+k atom if the notion of action-reaction balance is to hold. In other words, a unique j,k pairing combine to create a unique e_{j+k} (which in turn decays into these j,k with the same numbering). We argue that this is a kind of reaction balance, ie. equilibrium.. These two notions imply that:

$\ln(p_j)$ is proportional to j, which in turn leads to the MB distribution without the requirement of a factorial expression or Stirling's approximation.

References

1. Muller, R. The Boltzmann Factor: A Simple Derivation (2008 or later)
<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/index.php?eID=dumpFile&t=f&f=138377&token=ce78f1a73be3528669c0a5a4a6675d0e3284b02e>